

Disparity in Educational Attainment across Income Groups in India: An Analysis

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Abstract

Human capital has an important role to play in the development of any country whether developed or underdeveloped. Healthy, educated, skilled and productive labour force is an asset and can contribute to the overall progress of a country. But at the same time, disparities at any level are detrimental to the progress of a nation hampering its chance of achieving a balanced development. Inequalities have deepened between the richest and poorest making it more difficult for those at the bottom level to have a better living standard. Inadequate income can end up with the children belonging to the poorest population segments, with the wrong education and wrong skill development hampering the chances of improving their standard of living. The present study is an attempt to identify the educational disparity across various income quartiles and the digital disparity which act as an added disadvantage to the poorer sections using selected indicators.

Key Words: Disparity, Gross Attendance Rate, Net Attendance Rate, Dropout, Quintile class

Introduction

The progress of a nation depends upon its educated, healthy and skilled labour force. Any developmental measures taken will be beneficial if it accrues to all sections of people leading to a balanced economic development. Higher education can provide a variety of job opportunities to the people availing better income leading to higher standard of living. Poverty is one of the major problems facing developing countries. Provision of adequate employment opportunities with adequate income can tackle this problem for which education is one of the requisite factors. There exists a two way relationship between income and education. Higher education leads to higher income. Similarly to have access to better education, adequate income is essential to a certain extent. The covid-19 pandemic which unexpectedly leashed out disruptions in various sectors affected the educational sector, paving the way for a digitalized system of education, which became popular. Education sector, considered as a social sector, needs to be given importance as it plays an important part in shaping the future generations, their productivity and progress.

The social sector is usually defined as dealing with social and economic activities carried out for the purposes of benefiting society, and hence largely nonprofit, not-for-profit, philanthropic and mission based and nongovernmental organizations are associated with this sector. Even though, over the years, the motives of various private organizations providing education have changed from philanthropy to business oriented approach, which is a matter of concern for all.

Statement of the problem

The importance of education is widely understood by nations across the world. Educational services

come under the social sector, because the gains from education not only benefits the individual but the society as a whole. Hence, it is largely provided by the Government along with philanthropists and NGOs. This public provision of education makes it accessible to the unprivileged or socially deprived sections and low income segments. Even though the government has taken several measures to address the disparity over the years, they are unable to wipe it out completely. The present study aims to look into the educational attainment across income groups to understand the extent of disparity in terms of educational attainment at different levels of education.

The Income and education level has a two way relationship. Higher the income, higher the spending on education. Similarly, higher educational levels to a great extent lead to higher earnings. Thus income is an important determinant of participation in education. The present study has taken the Usual Monthly Per Capita expenditure on education as a proxy for the income level of people. Differences in income levels can widen the disparities in educational attainment across various low income groups especially with respect to access to educational facilities, which expanded during the pandemic times.

Objectives

1. To understand the disparity in education across income groups and rural-urban areas.
2. To identify the digital divide across income groups and rural-urban areas.
3. To suggest measures to deal with these disparities.

The present study is an attempt to find out the disparities in education which exist across income groups in rural-urban areas of India. It also tries to look into the digital divide in education in terms of

digital infrastructure like computer and internet facilities available to people across income quartiles. The data relating to this study pertains to the NSSO data collected during the period 2017-18.

Data Source and Methodology

The study has used secondary data from print and electronic media, especially the National Sample Survey. Various indicators like Gross Attendance Ratio, Net Attendance Ratio, dropout rate, availability of computer and internet facilities have been used to conduct the analysis. The study is mainly based on the NSS data of the 75th Round. Usual Monthly Per Capita expenditure expressed in quartiles of five groups has been taken as a proxy variable to show the different income groups.

Income level and Education

The income of a household plays a significant role in determining the education level of the children. Family income and parental income determine the facilities and support given to the children which of course has a great impact on the educational attainment of children. Especially in the present scenario where the country is moving towards a digital way of teaching and learning arising mainly from the covid-19 pandemic period, the access to such facilities has an important role to play. Several studies have corroborated the fact.

The present study is an attempt to look into the educational attainment and income level using NSS data 2017-18. Income level is an important determinant of expenditure on education. Several studies have brought out this relationship. Differences in income levels can widen the disparities in educational attainment across various low income groups especially with respect to access to educational facilities. The study tries to throw light on the digital disparity across income groups. As a proxy to the income, Usual Monthly Per-capita Consumption Expenditure is taken into account and households are divided into five quintile classes of 1 representing the lowest quintile class and 5 showing the highest quintile class (NSS Report No.585)

Participation of Students in various levels of Education

Participation of children in various levels of education is essential for the children as well as to the society as a whole because educated citizens contribute to a better skilled and able labour force. Gross Attendance Ratio gives a rough understanding with respect to the percentage of population enrolled and attending at various levels of education. See Figure 1.

Source: NSS Report No.585: Household Social Consumption on Education in India

In the case of primary education, almost hundred percent attendance is seen, irrespective of the quintile groups. More than hundred percent figure is due to the under aged children and over aged children being admitted to the primary level. With higher levels of education, there exist disparity across rural urban, quintile groups as well as among levels of school education. Gross attendance ratio is directly related to income levels. Urban areas are much ahead of the rural areas in terms of educational attainment. More importance should be given to education among the lowest quintile group from primary level to the higher levels.

Net Attendance Ratio

The age-specific participation in education can be understood from the Net Attendance Ratio which is a better measure than the Gross Attendance Ratio. Net attendance ratio (NAR) for a particular level of education is the ratio of the number of persons in the official age-group attending that level of education to the total number persons in that age-group. On the other hand, Gross Attendance Ratio (GAR) shows the total number of students attending primary school, irrespective of age and is expressed as a percentage of the official primary school-age population.

$$\text{NAR for I to V} = \frac{\text{Number of persons of age 6-10 currently attending classes I-V}}{\text{Estimated population in the age-group 6-10 years}} \times 100$$

To get a more accurate picture of the participation of children in the educational system, Net Attendance Ratio is used as it takes into account the age specific

enrolment in various levels of education. Figure 2 will throw light into this aspect.

Source: NSS Report No.585: Household Social Consumption on Education in India

The Net Attendance Ratio shows a different picture in comparison with the Gross Attendance Ratio. India still needs to take much effort in encouraging participation of children especially in the case of the lowest quintile group. At the post Higher Secondary Class level, the participation of the poorest category is the least, which is a matter of concern. Measures need to be taken to encourage the student participation in education especially at higher levels of school education, especially from secondary level onwards. To maintain the continuous participation

of students, proper measures should be taken to retain the students at lower levels of education so that stagnation and dropouts can be prevented to some extent.

Dropout and Never enrolled

Dropout affects the continuity in education as the enrolled people leave the education system without completing a particular level. Table 1 gives us an idea as to the proportion of dropout / discontinued and never enrolled from various quintile groups.

Table: 1 Proportion (per 1000) of persons (age 5-29) dropping out/ discontinued & never-enrolled for quintile classes of UMPCE

Quintile class of UMPCE	Proportion of drop out/ discontinuance		Proportion of never enrolled	
	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban
QC 1	297	360	155	124
QC 2	326	406	121	69
QC 3	338	406	116	44
QC 4	339	383	86	21
QC 5	334	360	59	9
All (2014)	326	383	109	56
All (2007-08)	327	390	158	80

Source: NSS Report No.585: Household Social Consumption on Education in India

There is not much disparity in the proportion of dropouts across quintile classes or between areas. The proportion of never enrolled people declined to around 16 percent in the poorest quartile whereas in the case of the richest quartile the fall was only 6 percent. The decline of never enrolled from 2007-08

to 2014 was significant showing that the income level and proportion of never enrolled are related to a certain extent. Percentage of persons never enrolled between sexes among quintile classes gives a clearer idea regarding the disparity across income groups indirectly. See Figure 3.

Source: NSS Report No.585: Household Social Consumption on Education in India

Females and rural areas witness a larger share of never enrolled persons compared to males and urban areas respectively. In all the cases, across rural and urban areas as well as between males and females, higher income quartile groups show a minimum percentage share of never enrolled persons compared to the lower income quartiles. With increasing income, the share of never enrolled also

declines showing that income level and participation in education are directly related.

Reasons behind Non-attendance

It is very important to understand the reasons behind the ever enrolled persons not attending education presently. This will give a clearer picture so that measures can be taken accordingly to improve the participation. Table 2 indicates this.

Table 2: Percentage of ever enrolled persons of age 3 to 35 years currently not attending education by major reasons (2017-18)

Indicator	Rural		Urban		Rural+ Urban		
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	
Percentage of ever enrolled persons currently not attending education	41.3	40	46.2	47.8	42.7	42.2	
Percentage distribution of ever enrolled persons by major reason for currently not attending	Not interested in education	20.6	15.9	14.9	12.6	18.8	14.8
	Financial constraints	25.6	18.4	21.4	16.1	24.3	17.7
	Engaged in domestic activities	4.7	31.9	2.3	26.7	4	30.2
	Engaged in economic activities	34.9	4.4	41.5	7.3	36.9	5.3
	School is far off	0.6	3.3	0.1	1.2	0.5	2.7
	Timings of educational institutions not suitable	0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0	0.1
	Medium of instruction used unfamiliar	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1
	Inadequate number of teachers	0	0.1	0	0	0	0
	Quality of teachers not satisfactory	0.1	0.1	0	0	0.1	0.1
	Route to educational institution not safe	0	0.2	0	0.1	0	0.2
	Unable to cope up with studies/failure in studies	4.1	3.7	3.1	2.6	3.8	3.4
	Unfriendly atmosphere at school	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1
	Completed desired level/class	4.2	4.2	9.5	11.2	5.8	6.4
	Preparation for competitive examination	1.8	0.6	3.2	1.9	2.2	1
	Non-availability of female teacher		0.1		0.1		0.1
	Non-availability of girls' toilet		0.1		0.1		0.1
	Marriage		12.4		15		13.2
	Others	3.1	4.4	3.6	4.9	3.3	4.5
all	100	100	100	100	100	100	

Source: NSS Report No.585: Household Social Consumption on Education in India

Major reasons behind not attending education were lack of interest in learning, financial constraints,

engagement in domestic and economic activities. More than 50 percent of the males did not attend

educational institutions due to financial constraints and involvement in economic activities, irrespective of urban or rural areas. In the case of females, major reasons were financial problems along with involvement in domestic activities, both in urban and rural areas. This clearly indicates the fact that income of the household is a deciding factor of educational attainment or completion.

Access to Computer and Internet Facility

Low income group parents are unable to provide the various facilities required by the children. Especially during the pandemic time, when educational institutions across the world were imparting

knowledge through online platforms and the internet, many of the children were facing problems to get access to learning. The covid-19 pandemic paved the way for popularizing online learning which later on became hybrid learning in many of the higher educational institutions. The government is also encouraging students to acquire knowledge through online resources and platforms like Swayam, Diksha, Swayamprabha, NPTEL and e-ShodhSindhu. But the problem faced by the children from poorer households was access to computer and internet facilities. See Figure 4.

Source: NSS Report No.585: Household Social Consumption on Education in India

Figure 4 points out to the fact that in rural areas and among the poor income groups, households having access to computers and the internet is very less compared to their urban and high income counterparts. The access to internet facility is 62 percent for high income category in urban areas whereas it is only 20 percent for their poor income counterparts. Similarly in rural areas 27 percent of high income have access to the internet which is only 7 percent for poor sections. 46 percent of high income groups have computer facilities in urban areas whereas it is only 8 percent for their poorer counterparts. Among high income groups in rural areas, 10 percent have computer access whereas it is only 2 percent for rural households. In short we can sum up that the digital mode of learning cannot be adopted by the government until and unless such facilities can be made available and accessible to all sections of the people or alternate arrangements to access such facilities are provided by the government.

Conclusions and Suggestions

Investing in developing human capability through imparting education is very essential for sustainable, resilient and national development. Disparities can

pose hurdles to the progress of any country as it may hamper balanced growth. Hence the government should take appropriate measures to bring down the disparity through various schemes and with the support of the private players through Corporate Social Responsibility activities. Lack of adequate income acts as an obstacle to children participating and attending the educational institutions among poor income group households. The various indicators of education have corroborated the fact that lower income quintiles are comparatively lagging behind the rich groups in terms of educational attainment.

Policy measures should be taken to provide quality facilities to poorer children and the residential system of school education can to some extent be an alternative to compensate for the financial problems affecting children. The government has come up with the New Education Policy, which has its positive and negative impact. The schools will be able to offer varied curriculum, which caters to students who have a range of interests, including those whose needs are not met by a traditional academic program. Further, the fluctuating mode of education will be beneficial as it will be able to

prevent dropout and stagnation to some extent. Children can pursue their interest through this flexible mode by having subject combinations which can be based on their area of interest rather than predefined combinations as in the case of the previous system of education followed in India.

One of the major drawbacks cited against the New Education Policy is the accessibility of education to the marginalized, underprivileged and poorer sections, if the government may withdraw from the public provision of educational services. Educational sector, if left to the private sector, may widen the disparities across different sections of society. An educated, skilled and healthy labour force can shape the progress of their family, society and the country as a whole. Public policies and programmes should take into account the needs of the youth diversities, while developing strategies and bringing changes in the education system. Efforts should be made to take into account the stakeholders' interest and opinion while framing policy measures. At the same time suitable revisions and alterations should be brought in the education system to meet the much required, contemporary skills demanded by the business sector.

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